

On ϕ - Classes of Submodules

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Abstract

Let R be a commutative ring with identity and let M be a unitary R -module. Let $S(M)$ be the set of all submodules of M and $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function. A proper submodule N of M is said to be a ϕ -prime (resp. a ϕ -primary) submodule if $am \in N - \phi(N)$ for $a \in R$, $m \in M$ implies that either $m \in N$ or $a \in (N : M)$ (resp. $a \in \sqrt{(N : M)}$). These concepts were introduced by N. Zamani and M. Bataineh, in this paper, we study the concept of ϕ -primary submodule in details. Also, we introduce the concepts of ϕ -primal submodules and ϕ -2-absorbing submodules.

Keywords: ϕ -prime submodules, ϕ -primary submodules, ϕ -primal submodules, ϕ -prime to submodule, ϕ -2-absorbing submodules.

1 Introduction

Let R be a commutative ring with identity and let M be a unitary R - module. Let $S(M)$ be the set of all submodules of M and $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function. A proper submodule N of M is said to be a ϕ -prime submodule if $am \in N - \phi(N)$ for $a \in R$, $m \in M$ implies that either $m \in N$ or $a \in (N : M)$. This definition was introduced by Zamani and Khaksari as a generalization of prime submodules that covers the definitions of prime, weakly prime, almost prime and m -almost prime submodules, see [14] and [20]. In our work, we study the concept of ϕ -primary submodule that was introduced in [15] in more details. We clarify that this definition is a generalized of primary submodules that covers the definition of primary, weakly primary, almost primary and m -almost primary submodules.

Let $\phi : J(R) \rightarrow J(R) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function with $J(R)$ the set of all ideals of R . Let I be an ideal of R , an element $a \in R$ is called ϕ -prime to I if $ra \in I - \phi(I)$ (with $r \in R$) implies that $r \in I$. We denote by $S_\phi(I)$ the set of all elements of R that are not ϕ -prime to I . I is called a ϕ -primal ideal of R if the set $P = S_\phi(I) \cup \phi(I)$ forms an ideal of R . The concept of ϕ -primal ideal over commutative ring was introduced by Darani (see[8]). In our work, we generalize the concept of ϕ -primal ideal to ϕ -primal submodule. We also, introduce the concept of ϕ -2-absorbing submodules which is a generalization to 2-absorbing submodules.

2 Basic Concepts

In this section, we recall some basic definitions and study some important results that we need throughout this paper.

Definition 2.1. [17] Let M be an R -module. A proper submodule N of M is said to be a *prime submodule* if whenever $rm \in N$ for $r \in R$ and $m \in M$ we get either $m \in N$ or $rM \subseteq N$ (equivalent $r \in (N : M)$).

Definition 2.2. [4] Let M be an R -module and N be a proper submodule of M . N is called a *weakly prime submodule* of M if, whenever $r \in R$ and $m \in M$ such that $0 \neq rm \in N$, then either $m \in N$ or $r \in (N : M)$.

Definition 2.3. [15] Let M be an R -module. A proper submodule N of M is called an *almost prime submodule* of M if, whenever $r \in R$ and $m \in M$ such that $rm \in N - (N : M)N$, then either $m \in N$ or $r \in (N : M)$.

Definition 2.4. [18] Let M be an R -module. A proper submodule N of M is said to be a *primary submodule* if $rm \in N$ for $r \in R$ and $m \in M$ implies that either $m \in N$ or $r^n M \subseteq N$ for some positive integer n .

Definition 2.5. [3] A proper submodule N of a module M over a commutative ring R is said to be a *weakly primary submodule* if whenever $0 \neq rm \in N$, for some $r \in R$, $m \in M$, then $m \in N$ or $r^n M \subseteq N$ for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Definition 2.6. [16] Let M be an R -module and N a proper submodule of M , N is called an *almost primary submodule* of M if, whenever $r \in R$, $m \in M$ such that $rm \in N - (N : M)N$, then either $m \in N$ or $r \in \sqrt{(N : M)}$.

Definition 2.7. [12] Let M be an R -module and N a submodule of M . The element $a \in R$ is (*left*) *prime to N* if $am \in N$ ($m \in M$) implies $m \in N$. The subset A of R is *uniformly not prime to N* , if there exists an element $u \in M - N$ with $Au \subseteq N$.

Definition 2.8. [12] Let M be an R -module and N a submodule of M . The *adjoint of N* is the set of all elements of R that are not prime to N and denoted by $adj(N)$. On other words, $adj(N) = \{r \in R : rm \in N \text{ for some } m \in M - N\}$.

Definition 2.9. [12] Let M be an R -module. A proper submodule N of M is said to be *primal* if $adj(N)$ forms an ideal of R . In this case the adjoint of N will also be called the *adjoint ideal of N* .

Definition 2.10. [5] Let N be a submodule of an R -module M . An element $r \in R$ is called *weakly prime (simply wp) to N* if $0 \neq rm \in N$ ($m \in M$) implies that $m \in N$. Otherwise r is not weakly prime (simply nwp) to N . Denote by $W(N)$ the set of elements of R that are nwp to N .

Definition 2.11. [5] Let R be a commutative ring and let N be a proper submodule of an R -module M . N is called *weakly primal* if the set $P = W(N) \cup \{0\}$ forms an ideal of R . P is called the (*weakly*) *adjoint ideal of N* and we also say that N is a *P -weakly primal submodule of M* .

The concept of almost primal ideals in a commutative ring was introduced by A.Y. Darani in [11]. Let R be a ring and let I be a proper ideal of R . An element $a \in R$ is called almost prime to I if $ra \in I - I^2$ (with $r \in R$) implies that $r \in I$. We denote by $A(I)$ the set of all elements of R that are not almost prime to I . A proper ideal I is called almost primal if the set $P = A(I) \cup I^2$ forms an ideal of R . This ideal P is an almost prime ideal of R , called the almost prime adjoint ideal of I . In this case we also say that I is a P -almost primal ideal. Now we give some definitions and result in almost primal submodules.

Definition 2.12. Let M be an R -module and N a submodule of M . The element $a \in R$ is (*left*) *almost prime to N* if $am \in N - (N : M)N$ ($m \in M$) implies $m \in N$. Denote by $A(N)$ the set of elements of R that are not almost prime to N .

Definition 2.13. Let R be a commutative ring and let N be a proper submodule of an R -module M . N is called *almost primal* if the set $P = A(N) \cup (N : M)N$ forms an ideal of R . P is called the (*almost*) *adjoint ideal of N* and we also say that N is a *P -almost primal submodule of M* .

Theorem 2.14. Let P be an ideal of a commutative ring R . Let N be a proper submodule of R -module M . The following are equivalent:

- (1) N is P -almost primal.
- (2) For every $x \notin P - (N : M)N$, $(N : x) = N \cup ((N : M)N : x)$ and for $x \in P - (N : M)N$, $(N : x) \supsetneq N \cup ((N : M)N : x)$.

Proof. (1) $\implies$ (2) Assume that N is P -almost primal then $P-(N : M)N = A(N)$. Let $x \notin P - (N : M)N$ then x is almost prime to N . Clearly $N \cup ((N : M)N : x) \subseteq (N : x)$. For every $m \in (N : x)$, if $mx \in (N : M)N$ then $m \in ((N : M)N : x)$ and if $mx \notin (N : M)N$ then x is almost prime to N , gives $m \in N$. Hence $m \in N \cup ((N : M)N : x)$, that is $(N : x) \subseteq N \cup ((N : M)N : x)$. Therefore $(N : x) = N \cup ((N : M)N : x)$. Now assume that $x \in P - (N : M)N$ then x is not almost prime to N so $\exists m \in M-N$ such that $xm \in N - (N : M)N$. So $m \in (N : x)$, but $m \notin ((N : M)N : x)$ nor $m \in N$. Hence, $(N : x) \neq N \cup ((N : M)N : x)$. However, it is clear that $N \cup ((N : M)N : x) \subsetneq (N : x)$.

(2) $\implies$ (1) We want to prove that $P-(N : M)N$ consists exactly of all elements of R that are not almost prime to N . Hence N is P -almost primal.

Let $x \notin P - (N : M)N$, then $(N : x) = N \cup ((N : M)N : x)$. We want to prove that $x \notin A(N)$. Let $xm \in N - (N : M)N$ with $m \in M$. So, $m \in (N : x)$. By assumption, either $(N : x) = N$ or $(N : x) = ((N : M)N : x)$. As $xm \in N - (N : M)N$, so $m \notin ((N : M)N : x)$. Thus, $m \in N$ and hence, $x \notin A(N)$. Conversely, let $x \in P - (N : M)N$, then $(N : x) \supsetneq N \cup ((N : M)N : x)$, so, $\exists m \in (N : x)$ such that $m \notin (N \cup ((N : M)N : x))$. Therefore, $m \notin N$ and $m \notin ((N : M)N : x)$. Thus $xm \in N - (N : M)N$ with $m \notin N$, so x is not almost prime to N and hence $x \in A(N)$. $\square$

Proposition 2.15. Let N be a submodule of R -module M . If N is almost primal submodule, then $P = A(N) \cup (N : M)N$ is almost prime ideal of R .

Proof. Suppose that $r, s \notin P$, we show that either $rs \in P^2$ or $rs \notin P$. Assume that $rs \notin P^2$. Let $rsm \in N - (N : M)N$ for some $m \in M$. Then, by Theorem 2.14 gives that $rm \in (N : s) = N \cup ((N : M)N : s)$ where $rm \notin ((N : M)N : s)$; hence $rm \in N$ which implies that $rm \in N - (N : M)N$. Thus $m \in (N : r) = N \cup ((N : M)N : r)$, and so $m \in N$. Therefore, rs is almost prime to N and $rs \notin P$ as required. $\square$

Definition 2.16. [1] Let R be ring. Let $\phi : I(R) \rightarrow I(R) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function where $I(R)$ is the set of all ideals of R . A proper ideal I of R is a ϕ -prime ideal if $a, b \in R$ with $ab \in I - \phi(I)$ implies $a \in I$ or $b \in I$.

Definition 2.17. [20] Let R be a commutative ring with identity and M be a unitary R -module. Let $S(M)$ be the set of all submodules of M , and let $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function. A proper submodule N of M is called ϕ -prime submodule if $a \in R, x \in M$ with $ax \in N - \phi(N)$ implies that $a \in (N : M)$ or $x \in N$.

Definition 2.18. [9] Let R be a commutative ring with unity and M an R -module. A proper submodule N of M is said to be a 2-absorbing submodule if whenever $a, b \in R$ and $m \in M$ with $abm \in N$ then $ab \in (N : M)$ or $am \in N$ or $bm \in N$.

Definition 2.19. [9] Let R be a commutative ring and M an R -module. A proper submodule N of M is said to be weakly 2-absorbing submodule if whenever $a, b \in R, m \in M$ with $0 \neq abm \in N$ then $ab \in (N : M)$ or $am \in N$ or $bm \in N$.

The following proposition study the relations between the previous submodules, which were proved in [7], [3], [4], [16], [10], [9].

Proposition 2.20. Let M be a module over a commutative ring and N a submodule of M . Then

- (1) N is prime $\rightarrow N$ is weakly prime submodule $\rightarrow N$ is almost prime submodule.
- (2) N is primary $\rightarrow N$ is weakly primary submodule $\rightarrow N$ is almost primary submodule.

- (3) N is almost prime submodule $\rightarrow N$ is almost primary submodule.
 (4) N is prime submodule $\rightarrow N$ is primary submodule $\rightarrow N$ is primal submodule.
 (5) N is prime submodule $\rightarrow N$ is 2-absorbing submodule $\rightarrow N$ is weakly 2-absorbing submodule.
 (6) N is weakly prime submodule $\rightarrow N$ is weakly 2-absorbing submodule.

3 ϕ - Primary Submodules

Let $S(M)$ be the set of all submodules of M , and $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function. Then we have the following definition.

Definition 3.1. [7] A proper submodule N of M is called ϕ - primary submodule if $a \in R, x \in M$ with $ax \in N - \phi(N)$ implies that $x \in N$ or $a^k \in (N : M)$, for some positive integer k . In other word, $x \in N$ or $a \in \sqrt{(N : M)}$.

Example 3.2. Let R be a commutative ring. Let M be an R -module. Let $S(M)$ be the set of all submodules of M . Define the following type of the functions $\phi_\alpha : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ and the corresponding ϕ_α - primary submodules as follows :

- 1) $\phi_\emptyset : \phi_\emptyset(N) = \emptyset, \forall N \in S(M)$, defines primary submodules.
- 2) $\phi_0 : \phi_0(N) = \{0\}, \forall N \in S(M)$, defines weakly primary submodules.
- 3) $\phi_1 : \phi_1(N) = N, \forall N \in S(M)$, defines any submodule N .
- 4) $\phi_2 : \phi_2(N) = (N : M)N, \forall N \in S(M)$, defines almost primary submodules.
- 5) $\phi_w : \phi_w(N) = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} (N : M)^i N, \forall N \in S(M)$, defines ϕ_w -primary submodules.
- 6) $\phi_n : \phi_n(N) = (N : M)^{n-1}N, n \geq 2, \forall N \in S(M)$, defines n -almost primary submodules.

Remarks 3.3. (1) Since $N - \phi(N) = N - (N \cap \phi(N))$, so without loss of generality, throughout this thesis we will consider $\phi(N) \subseteq N$ for any $N \in S(M)$.

(2) For functions $\phi, \psi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$, we write $\phi \leq \psi$ if $\phi(N) \subseteq \psi(N) \forall N \in S(M)$.

(3) Observe that $\phi_\emptyset \leq \phi_0 \leq \phi_w \leq \dots \leq \phi_{n+1} \leq \phi_n \leq \dots \leq \phi_2 \leq \phi_1$.

Proposition 3.4. Let R be a commutative ring and N be a submodule of R -module M .

(1) Let $\psi_1, \psi_2 : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be functions with $\psi_1 \leq \psi_2$. Then N is ψ_1 -primary implies N is ψ_2 -primary.

(2) Let $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be functions. If N is ϕ -prime then N is ϕ -primary.

(3) N is primary $\implies N$ is weakly primary $\implies N$ is ϕ_w -primary $\implies N$ is ϕ_{n+1} -primary $\implies \phi_n$ -primary ($n \geq 2$) $\implies N$ is almost primary.

Proof. (1) Assume that N is ψ_1 -primary. Let $rm \in N - \psi_2(N)$ for $r \in R, m \in M$ then $rm \in N - \psi_1(N)$. Since N is ψ_1 -primary, $r^k \in (N : M)$ for some $k \in \mathbb{N}$ or $m \in N$. Hence N is ψ_2 -primary.

(2) Is trivial and follows immediately from the definition.

(3) This follows from (1) and the ordering of the ϕ_α 's given in Remark 3.3. □

Theorem 3.5. Let R be a commutative ring and M be an R -module. Let $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function. Let N be a ϕ -primary submodule of M . If $(N : M)N \not\subseteq \phi(N)$ then N is a primary submodule of M .

Proof. Let $a \in R$ and $x \in M$ be such that $ax \in N$. If $ax \notin \phi(N)$, then since N is ϕ -primary, we have $a^k \in (N : M)$ for some $k \in \mathbb{N}$ or $x \in N$. So let $ax \in \phi(N)$. In this case we may assume that $aN \subseteq \phi(N)$, because if $aN \not\subseteq \phi(N)$ then there exists $p \in N$ such that $ap \notin \phi(N)$, so that $a(x+p) \in N - \phi(N)$. Therefore $a \in \sqrt{(N : M)}$ or $x + p \in N$ and hence $a \in \sqrt{(N : M)}$ or $x \in N$. Second we may assume that $(N : M)x \in \phi(N)$. If this is not the case, there exists $u \in (N : M)$ such that $ux \notin \phi(N)$ and so $(a+u)x \in N - \phi(N)$. Since N is a ϕ -primary submodule, we have $a+u \in \sqrt{(N : M)}$ or $x \in N$. So $a \in \sqrt{(N : M)}$ or $x \in N$. Now since $(N : M)N \not\subseteq \phi(N)$, there exist $r \in (N : M)$ and $p \in N$ such that $rp \notin \phi(N)$.

So $(a + r)(x + p) \in N - \phi(N)$, and hence $a + r \in \sqrt{(N : M)}$ or $x + p \in N$. Therefore $a \in \sqrt{(N : M)}$ or $x \in N$. Thus N is primary submodule. $\square$

Corollary 3.6. *Let N be a weakly primary submodule of M such that $(N : M)N \neq 0$. Then N is a primary submodule of M .*

Proof. In the above theorem, set $\phi = \phi_0$. $\square$

Remark 3.7. Suppose that N is a ϕ -primary submodule of M such that $\phi(N) \subseteq (N : M)N$ (resp. $\phi(N) \subseteq (N : M)^2N$) and that N is not a primary submodule. Then by Theorem 3.5, we have $\phi(N) = (N : M)N$ (resp. $\phi(N) = (N : M)^2N$). In particular if N is a weakly primary (resp. ϕ_3 -primary) submodule but not primary submodule then $(N : M)N = 0$ (resp. $(N : M)N = (N : M)^2N$).

Theorem 3.8. [3] *Let $R = R_1 \times R_2$ where each R_i is a commutative ring with identity. Let M_i be R_i -module $\forall i \in \{1, 2\}$, and $M = M_1 \times M_2$ be an R -module with $(r_1, r_2)(m_1, m_2) = (r_1m_1, r_2m_2)$, where $r_i \in R_i, m_i \in M_i$. Then,*
(1) *If N_1 is a primary submodule of M_1 , then $N_1 \times M_2$ is a primary submodule of M .*
(2) *If N_2 is a primary submodule of M_2 , then $M_1 \times N_2$ is a primary submodule of M .*

Remark 3.9. The above theorem is not true for correspondence ϕ -primary submodules in general, for example if N_1 is a ϕ_0 -primary submodule of M_1 then $N_1 \times M_2$ is not necessarily a ϕ_0 -primary submodule of $M_1 \times M_2$. Let $R_1 = R_2 = M_1 = M_2 = Z_{14}$, and suppose $N_1 = 0$. Then evidently N_1 is a ϕ_0 -primary submodule of M_1 . However, $(2, 1)(7, 1) \in N_1 \times M_2$, and $(7, 1) \notin N_1 \times M_2$. Also $(2, 1)^k(2, 1) \notin N_1 \times M_2$ for any $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $(2, 1)^k M \not\subseteq N_1 \times M_2$.

Proposition 3.10. *Let R_1 and R_2 be two commutative rings, with $R = R_1 \times R_2$, M_1 and M_2 be R_1 and R_2 -modules respectively. Let $M = M_1 \times M_2$ be an R -modules with $(r_1, r_2)(m_1, m_2) = (r_1m_1, r_2m_2)$ where $r_i \in R_i, m_i \in M_i$. Let $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function. Suppose that N_1 is a weakly primary submodule of M_1 such that $\{0\} \times M_2 \subseteq \phi(N_1 \times M_2)$. Then $N_1 \times M_2$ is a ϕ -primary submodule of $M_1 \times M_2$.*

Proof. Let $(r_1, r_2)(x_1, x_2) = (r_1x_1, r_2x_2) \in N_1 \times M_2 - \phi(N_1 \times M_2)$, but $N_1 \times M_2 - \phi(N_1 \times M_2) \subseteq N_1 \times M_2 - \{0\} \times M_2 = (N_1 - \{0\}) \times M_2$. We have $r_1x_1 \in N_1 - \{0\}$ and by the assumption on N_1 we have $r_1^k \in (N_1 :_{R_1} M_1)$ for some positive integer k or $x_1 \in N_1$. This gives that $(r_1, r_2)^k = (r_1^k, r_2^k) \in (N_1 :_{R_1} M_1) \times R_2 = (N_1 \times M_2 :_{R_1 \times R_2} M_1 \times M_2)$ for some positive integer k or $(x_1, x_2) \in N_1 \times M_2$. Therefore $N_1 \times M_2$ is a ϕ -primary submodule of $M_1 \times M_2$. $\square$

Proposition 3.11. *Let R_1 and R_2 be two commutative rings, M_1 and M_2 be R_1 and R_2 -modules respectively. Let $M = M_1 \times M_2$ and $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function. such that $\phi_w \leq \phi$. Then for any weakly primary submodule N_1 of M_1 , $N_1 \times M_2$ is a ϕ -primary submodule of $M_1 \times M_2$.*

Proof. If N_1 is a primary submodule of M_1 , then $N_1 \times M_2$ is primary submodule of M , (see Theorem 3.8), and so a ϕ -primary submodule of $M_1 \times M_2$. Suppose that N_1 is not a primary submodule of M_1 . Then by Remark 3.7, we have $(N_1 :_{R_1} M_1)N_1 = \{0\}$. This gives that $(N_1 \times M_2 :_{R_1 \times R_2} M_1 \times M_2)^i(N_1 \times M_2) = [(N_1 :_{R_1} M_1)^i N_1] \times M_2 = \{0\} \times M_2$, for all $i \geq 1$ and hence we have $\{0\} \times M_2 = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} (N_1 \times M_2 :_{R_1 \times R_2} M_1 \times M_2)^i(N_1 \times M_2) = \phi_w(N_1 \times M_2) \subseteq \phi(N_1 \times M_2)$, and by Proposition 3.10, we have $N_1 \times M_2$ is a ϕ -primary submodule of $M_1 \times M_2$. $\square$

Theorem 3.12. *Let $R = R_1 \times R_2$ such that each R_i is a commutative ring with identity. Let M_i be R_i -module $\forall i \in \{1, 2\}$, and $M = M_1 \times M_2$ with $(r_1, r_2)(m_1, m_2) = (r_1m_1, r_2m_2)$, be an R -module, where $r_i \in R_i, m_i \in M_i \forall i \in \{1, 2\}$, and let $\psi_i : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a functions, $\phi = \psi_1 \times \psi_2$. Then each of the following types are ϕ -primary submodules of $M_1 \times M_2$,*
(i) $N_1 \times N_2$ where N_i is a proper submodule of M_i , with $\psi_i(N_i) = N_i$.
(ii) $P_1 \times M_2$ where P_1 is a primary submodule of M_1 .

- (iii) $P_1 \times M_2$ where P_1 is a ψ_1 -primary submodule of M_1 and $\psi_2(M_2) = M_2$.
- (iv) $M_1 \times P_2$ where P_2 is a primary submodule of M_2 .
- (v) $M_1 \times P_2$ where P_2 is a ψ_2 -primary submodule of M_2 and $\psi_1(M_1) = M_1$.

Proof. (i) is clear, since $N_1 \times N_2 - \phi(N_1 \times N_2) = \emptyset$

(ii) If P_1 is a primary submodule of M_1 , then by Theorem 3.8, $P_1 \times M_2$ a primary submodule of $M_1 \times M_2$, and thus $P_1 \times M_2$ is ϕ -primary submodule of M .

(iii) Let P_1 be a ψ_1 -primary submodule of M_1 and $\psi_2(M_2) = M_2$. Let $(r_1, r_2) \in R$ and $(x_1, x_2) \in M$ be such that $(r_1, r_2)(x_1, x_2) = (r_1x_1, r_2x_2) \in P_1 \times M_2 - \phi(P_1 \times M_2) = P_1 \times M_2 - \psi_1(P_1) \times \psi_2(M_2) = P_1 \times M_2 - \psi_1(P_1) \times M_2 = (P_1 - \psi_1(P_1)) \times M_2$. So $r_1x_1 \in P_1 - \psi_1(P_1)$ but P_1 is ψ_1 -primary submodule, so $r_1^k \in (P_1 :_{R_1} M_1)$ for some $k \in \mathbb{N}$ or $x_1 \in P_1$. Therefore $(r_1, r_2)^k \in (P_1 :_{R_1} M_1) \times R_2 = (P_1 \times M_2 :_{R_1 \times R_2} M_1 \times M_2)$ or $(x_1, x_2) \in P_1 \times M_2$. So $P_1 \times M_2$ is a ϕ -primary submodule of $M_1 \times M_2$.

Parts (iv), (v) are proved similar to (ii), (iii) respectively. □

Theorem 3.13. *Let N be a proper submodule of M and let $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function. Then the following are equivalent:*

- (i) N is ϕ -primary submodule of M .
- (ii) For $r \in R - \sqrt{(N : M)}$, $(N : (r)) = N \cup (\phi(N) : (r))$.
- (iii) For $r \in R - \sqrt{(N : M)}$, $(N : (r)) = N$ or $(N : (r)) = (\phi(N) : (r))$.

Proof. (i) $\implies$ (ii) Suppose that N is ϕ -primary such that $r \notin \sqrt{(N : M)}$. Let $m \in (N : (r))$. So $rm \in N$. If $rm \notin \phi(N)$, then N is ϕ -primary implies $m \in N$, and if $rm \in \phi(N)$, then $m \in (\phi(N) : (r))$. Hence $(N : (r)) \subseteq N \cup (\phi(N) : (r))$. The other inclusion hold trivially, since $\phi(N) \subseteq N$.

(ii) $\implies$ (iii) It is clear because $(N : (r))$ is an ideal of R .

(iii) $\implies$ (i) Let $r \in R$, $m \in M$ such that $rm \in N - \phi(N)$. If $r \notin \sqrt{(N : M)}$, then by assumption, either $(N : (r)) = N$ or $(N : (r)) = (\phi(N) : (r))$. As $rm \notin \phi(N)$, then $m \notin (\phi(N) : (r))$ and as $rm \in N$, then $m \in (N : (r))$. Hence $(N : (r)) = N$, and so $m \in N$ as required. □

Theorem 3.14. *Let M be an R -module and let N be a proper submodule of M . If for any ideal I of R and submodule K of M with $IK \subseteq N$ and $IK \not\subseteq \phi(N)$, we have $I \subseteq \sqrt{(N : M)}$ or $K \subseteq N$, then N is ϕ -primary submodule of M .*

Proof. Suppose that $rm \in N - \phi(N)$ for $r \in R$ and $m \in N$. Then $(r)(m) = (rm) \subseteq N - \phi(N)$. By the assumption, either $(m) \subseteq N$ or $(r) \subseteq \sqrt{(N : M)}$. Therefore, $m \in N$ or $r \in \sqrt{(N : M)}$ and N is ϕ -primary submodule of M . □

Proposition 3.15. *Let N be a submodule of M with $(N : M) = \sqrt{(N : M)}$, then N is ϕ -primary if and only if N is ϕ -prime.*

Proof. Trivial from the definitions of ϕ -prime and ϕ -primary submodules. □

Theorem 3.16. *Let M be an R -module and let $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$. Let P be a ϕ -primary submodule of M .*

- (i) If $L \subseteq P$ is a submodule of M , then P/L is a ϕ_L -primary submodule of M/L .
- (ii) Suppose that S is a multiplicatively closed subset of R such that $S^{-1}P \neq S^{-1}M$ and $S^{-1}(\phi(P)) \subseteq (S^{-1}\phi)(S^{-1}P)$ and $(P : M) \cap S = \emptyset$. Then $S^{-1}P$ is an $(S^{-1}\phi)$ -primary submodule of $S^{-1}M$.

Proof. (i) Let $a \in R$ and $\bar{x} \in M/L$ with $a\bar{x} \in P/L - \phi_L(P/L)$, where $\bar{x} = x + L$, for some $x \in M$. By the definition of ϕ_L , this gives that $ax \in P - \phi(P)$, which gives that $a^k \in (P : M)$ for some $k \in \mathbb{N}$ or $x \in P$. Therefore $a^k \in (P/L : M/L)$ for some $k \in \mathbb{N}$ or $\bar{x} \in P/L$ and so P/L is ϕ_L -primary submodule.

(ii) Let $a/s \in S^{-1}R$ and $x/t \in S^{-1}M$ with $ax/st \in S^{-1}P - (S^{-1}\phi)(S^{-1}P)$. Then by our assumption $ax/st \in S^{-1}P - S^{-1}(\phi(P))$. Therefore there exists $u \in S$ such that $uax \in P -$

$\phi(P)$, (note that for each $v \in S$, $vax \notin \phi(P)$). Since P is ϕ -primary and $(P : M) \cap S = \emptyset$, we have $(ua)^k \in (P : M)$ for some $k \in \mathbb{N}$ or $x \in P$. Therefore $(a/s)^k \in S^{-1}((P :_R M)) \subseteq (S^{-1}P :_{S^{-1}R} S^{-1}M)$ for some $k \in \mathbb{N}$ (because $(P : M) \subseteq (S^{-1}P : S^{-1}M)$) or $x/t \in S^{-1}P$. Hence $S^{-1}P$ is an $(S^{-1}\phi)$ -primary submodule of $S^{-1}M$. $\square$

4 ϕ - Primal Submodules

The concept of ϕ -primal ideals in a commutative ring was introduced by A.Y. Darani in [8]. Let R be a commutative ring with identity. Let $\phi : \mathbb{J}(R) \rightarrow \mathbb{J}(R) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function where $\mathbb{J}(R)$ denotes the set of all ideals of R . Let I be an ideal of R . An element $a \in R$ is called ϕ -prime to I if $ra \in I - \phi(I)$ (with $r \in R$) implies that $r \in I$. We denote by $S_\phi(I)$ the set of all elements of R that are not ϕ -prime to I . I is called a ϕ -primal ideal of R if the set $P = S_\phi(I) \cup \phi(I)$ forms an ideal of R . In this case P is called the ϕ -prime adjoint ideal (simply adjoint ideal) of I , and I is called a P - ϕ -primal ideal of R .

Now we generalize the concept of ϕ -primal ideals to ϕ -primal submodules. Let M be R -module, let $S(M)$ be the set of all submodule of M and $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function.

Definition 4.1. Let N be a submodule of R -module M and $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function. An element $r \in R$ is called ϕ -prime to N if $rm \in N - \phi(N)$ (with $m \in M$) implies that $m \in N$. Otherwise r is not ϕ -prime to N .

Remarks 4.2. Let N be a submodule of R -module M . Denote by $S_\emptyset(N)$ the set of all elements of R that are not ϕ -prime to N , then

- (1) If an element of R is prime to N then it is ϕ -prime to N , so $S_\emptyset(N) \subseteq \text{adj}(N) = S(N)$.
- (2) The converse of (1) is not necessarily true in general. For example consider the $\mathbb{Z}$ -module $M = \mathbb{Z}/24\mathbb{Z}$, its submodule $N = 8\mathbb{Z}/24\mathbb{Z}$ and assume that $\phi = \phi_0$ where $\phi_0(N) = 0$. Denote each coset $a + 24\mathbb{Z}$ in M by $\bar{a}$. Then, as $6 \cdot \bar{12} = \bar{0} \in N$ and $\bar{12} \in M - N$, so 6 is not prime to N . But if $6 \cdot \bar{a} \in N$ for some $\bar{a} \in M$, then 4 divides a . Hence $6 \cdot \bar{a} = \bar{0}$. This implies that 6 is ϕ_0 -prime to N . Thus, we have $\text{adj}(N) \not\subseteq S_\emptyset(N)$.

Definition 4.3. Let R be a commutative ring and let $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function. A proper submodule N of M is said to be a ϕ -primal if the set $P = S_\phi(N) \cup \phi(N)$ forms an ideal of R .

Example 4.4. Let R be a commutative ring. Let M be an R -module. Let $S(M)$ be the set of all submodules of M . Define the following type of the functions $\phi_\alpha : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ and the corresponding ϕ_α -primal submodules as follows :

- 1) $\phi_\emptyset : \phi_\emptyset(N) = \emptyset, \forall N \in S(M)$, defines primal submodules.
- 2) $\phi_0 : \phi_0(N) = \{0\}, \forall N \in S(M)$, then defines weakly primal submodules.
- 3) $\phi_1 : \phi_1(N) = N, \forall N \in S(M)$, defines any submodule N .
- 4) $\phi_2 : \phi_2(N) = (N : M)N, \forall N \in S(M)$, defines almost primal submodules.
- 5) $\phi_w : \phi_w(N) = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} (N : M)^i N, \forall N \in S(M)$, defines ϕ_w -primal submodule.
- 6) $\phi_n : \phi_n(N) = (N : M)^{n-1}N, \forall n \geq 2, \forall N \in S(M)$, defines n -almost primal submodules.

Theorem 4.5. Let P be an ideal of a commutative ring R . Let N be a proper submodule of R -module M . Let $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function. Then the following are equivalent:

- (1) N is P - ϕ -primal submodule.
- (2) For every $x \notin P - \phi(N)$, $(N : x) = N \cup (\phi(N) : x)$ and for $x \in P - \phi(N)$, $(N : x) \supseteq N \cup (\phi(N) : x)$.
- (3) For every $x \notin P - \phi(N)$, $(N : x) = N$ or $(N : x) = (\phi(N) : x)$ and for $x \in P - \phi(N)$, $(N : x) \supseteq N$ and $(N : x) \supseteq (\phi(N) : x)$.

Proof. (1 $\rightarrow$ 2) Assume that N is P - ϕ -primal submodule then $P - \phi(N)$ consists entirely of elements of R that are not ϕ -prime to N . Let $x \notin P - \phi(N)$ then x is ϕ -prime to N . Clearly $N \cup (\phi(N) : x) \subseteq (N : x)$. On the other hand, for every $m \in (N : x)$, if $mx \in \phi(N)$ then m

$\in (\phi(N) : x)$ and if $mx \notin \phi(N)$ then x is ϕ -prime to N gives $m \in N$. Hence $m \in N \cup (\phi(N) : x)$, that is $(N : x) \subseteq N \cup (\phi(N) : x)$. Therefore $(N : x) = N \cup (\phi(N) : x)$. Now assume that $x \in P - \phi(N)$ then x is not ϕ -prime to N , so $\exists m \in M - N$ such that $mx \in N - \phi(N)$. Hence $m \in (N : x) - (N \cup (\phi(N) : x))$. Thus $(N : x) \not\subseteq N \cup (\phi(N) : x)$

(2 $\rightarrow$ 3) It is clear because $(N : x)$ is an ideal in R .

(3 $\rightarrow$ 1) We want to prove that $P - \phi(N)$ consists exactly of all elements of R that are not ϕ -prime to N . Hence N is $P - \phi$ -primal.

Let $x \notin P - \phi(N)$, then $(N : x) = N \cup (\phi(N) : x)$. We want to prove that $x \notin S_\phi(N)$. Let $xm \in N - \phi(N)$ with $m \in M$. So, $m \in (N : x)$. By assumption, either $(N : x) = N$ or $(N : x) = (\phi(N) : x)$. As $xm \in N - \phi(N)$, so $m \notin (\phi(N) : x)$. Thus, $m \in N$ and hence, $x \notin S_\phi(N)$. Conversely, let $x \in P - \phi(N)$, then $(N : x) \not\subseteq N \cup (\phi(N) : x)$, so, $\exists m \in (N : x)$ such that $m \notin (N \cup (\phi(N) : x))$. Therefore, $m \notin N$ and $m \notin (\phi(N) : x)$. Thus $xm \in N - \phi(N)$ with $m \notin N$, so x is not ϕ -prime to N and hence $x \in S_\phi(N)$. Hence N is $P - \phi$ -primal submodule. $\square$

Proposition 4.6. *Let R be a commutative ring and M be R -module. Let $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function. If N is ϕ -primal submodule of M then $P = S_\emptyset(N) \cup \phi(N)$ is ϕ -prime ideal of R .*

Proof. Suppose that $r, s \notin P$, we show that either $rs \in \phi(P)$ or $rs \notin P$. Assume that $rs \notin \phi(P)$. Let $rsm \in N - \phi(N)$ for some $m \in M$. Then, by Theorem 4.5 gives that $rm \in (N : s) = N \cup (\phi(N) : s)$ where $rm \notin (\phi(N) : s)$; hence $rm \in N$ which implies that $rm \in N - \phi(N)$. Thus $m \in (N : r) = N \cup (\phi(N) : r)$, and so $m \in N$. Therefore, rs is ϕ -prime to N and $rs \notin P$ as required. $\square$

Notation 4.7. Let N be a ϕ -primal submodule of R -module M . By Proposition 4.6, $P = S_\emptyset(N) \cup \phi(N)$ is ϕ -prime ideal of R . In this case P is called the ϕ -prime adjoint ideal and N is called a $P - \phi$ -primal submodule of M .

The concepts "primal submodule" and " ϕ -primal submodule" are different. In fact, neither implies the other. We will show this by the following examples, in Example 4.8 below we give a primal submodule that is not ϕ -primal. An example of ϕ -primal submodule which is not primal is given in Example 4.9.

Example 4.8. [5],[8] *Consider the submodule $N = 8\mathbb{Z}/24\mathbb{Z}$ of $\mathbb{Z}$ -module $M = \mathbb{Z}/24\mathbb{Z}$. Denote each coset $a + 24\mathbb{Z}$ in M by $\bar{a}$. Let $\phi = \phi_0$ (weakly primal).*

(1) *since $0 \neq 2\bar{4} \in N$ and $0 \neq 4\bar{2} \in N$ with $\bar{2}, \bar{4} \in M - N$ we have $2, 4 \in S_{\phi_0}(N)$. If $6\bar{a} \in N$ for some $\bar{a} \in M$ then 4 divides a and hence $6\bar{a} = 0$. This shows that $2+4 = 6$ is ϕ_0 -prime to N so $6 \notin S_{\phi_0}(N)$. Therefore $S_\phi(N) \cup \phi(N)$ is not an ideal of $\mathbb{Z}$, that is N is not ϕ -primal submodule of M .*

(2) *Now set $P = 2\mathbb{Z}/24\mathbb{Z}$ then every element of P is not prime to N . Assume that $\bar{a} \notin P$, if $\bar{a}\bar{n} \in N$ for some $\bar{n} \in M$ then 8 divides n , that is $\bar{n} \in N$. Hence $\bar{a}$ is prime to N so $\bar{a} \notin S(N) = \text{adj}(N)$. So we have $S(N) = P$, that is N is P -primal submodule. This example show that a primal submodule need not necessarily be ϕ -primal.*

Example 4.9. [5] *Consider the $\mathbb{Z}$ -module $M = \mathbb{Z}_6$ and denote every integer a modulo 6 by $\bar{a}$. Consider the submodule $N = \{0\}$ of M and let $\phi = \phi_0$ then:*

(1) *0 is weakly prime to N so $S_{\phi_0}(N) = \emptyset$. Thus N is weakly primal submodule of M .*

(2) *Since $2\bar{3} = \bar{0} \in N$ and $3\bar{2} = \bar{0} \in N$, so $2, 3 \in S_\emptyset(N)$ while $3-2 = 1$ is prime to N , so we have $1 \notin S(N)$. Therefore N is not a primal submodule of M .*

This example shows that ϕ -primal submodule need not necessarily be primal.

Theorem 4.10. *Let M be R -module and $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function. Let N and L be submodules of M with $L \subseteq \phi(N)$ then N is a ϕ -primal submodule of M iff N/L is a ϕ_L -primal submodule of M/L .*

Proof. Assume N is $P - \phi$ -primal submodule. Suppose that $a + L$ is an element of M/L that is not ϕ_L -prime to N/L , so there exists $b \in M - N$ with $(a + L)(b + L) \in N/L - \phi_L(N/L)$.

In this case $ab \in N - \phi(N)$ with $b \in M - N$ implies that a is not ϕ -prime to N . Hence $a \in S_\phi(N) \subseteq P$ and so $a + L \in P/L$. Now assume that $c + L \in P/L$ then $c \in P = S_\phi(N) \cup \phi(N)$. If $c \in \phi(N)$ then $c + L \in \phi_L(N/L)$, so assume that $c \in S_\phi(N)$, that is c is not ϕ -prime to N then $cd \in N - \phi(N)$ for some $d \in M - N$. Consequently, $(c + L)(d + L) \in N/L - (\phi(N)/L) = N/L - \phi_L(N/L)$ with $d + L \in M/L - N/L$. This implies that $c + L$ is not ϕ_L -prime to N/L , so $c + L \in S_{\phi_L}(N/L)$. We have already shown that $P/L = S_{\phi_L}(N/L) \cup \phi_L(N/L)$. Therefore N/L is ϕ_L -primal.

Conversely, suppose that N/L is ϕ_L -primal in M/L with the adjoint ideal P/L . For every $a \in P - \phi(N)$ we have $a + L \in P/L - \phi_L(N/L) = S_{\phi_L}(N/L)$, so $a + L$ is not ϕ_L -prime to N/L , thus $(a + L)(b + L) \in N/L - \phi_L(N/L)$ for some $b + L \in M/L - N/L$. In this case $b \in M - N$ and $ab \in N - \phi(N)$ implies that a is not ϕ -prime to N . On the other hand, assume that $c \in R$ is not ϕ -prime to N then $cd \in N - \phi(N)$ for some $d \in M - N$ so we have $(c + L)(d + L) \in N/L - \phi_L(N/L)$ with $d + L \notin N/L$, that is $c + L$ is not ϕ_L -prime to N/L . Hence $c + L \in P/L - \phi_L(N/L)$, so we have $c \in P - \phi(N)$. It follows that $P = S_\phi(N) \cup \phi(N)$ which implies that N is P - ϕ -primal submodule of M . $\square$

Remark 4.11. [5] Let R be a commutative ring, M an R -module and S a multiplicatively closed set in R . If K is a submodule of $S^{-1}M$, define $K \cap M = v^{-1}(K) = \{m \in M : m/1 \in K\}$, where $v : M \rightarrow S^{-1}M$ is the natural mapping $m \mapsto m/1$. Clearly, $K \cap M$ is a submodule of M .

Proposition 4.12. *Let R be a commutative ring and S a multiplicatively closed subset of R . Let $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function. Let N be a P - ϕ -primal submodule of an R -module M with $P \cap S = \emptyset$.*

- (1) *Let $\lambda = a/s \in S^{-1}N - S^{-1}(\phi(N))$ (with $a \in M, s \in S$), then $a \in N$.*
- (2) *If $S^{-1}(\phi(N)) \neq S^{-1}N$ then $N = S^{-1}N \cap M$.*

Proof. (1) Assume that $\lambda = a/s \in S^{-1}N - S^{-1}(\phi(N))$ then $a/s = b/t$ for some $b \in N, t \in S$. In this case, since $us \in S$ and $b \in N$, then $uta = usb \in N$ for some $u \in S$. If $uta \in \phi(N)$ then $a/s = uta/uts \in S^{-1}(\phi(N))$ which is a contradiction, so we have $uta \in N - \phi(N)$. If $a \notin N$ then ut is not ϕ -prime to N , so $ut \in P \cap S$ which contradicts the hypothesis. Therefore $a \in N$.

(2) Let $m \in S^{-1}N \cap M$ then $m/1 \in S^{-1}N$, so $\exists s \in S$ such that $sm \in N$. If $sm \notin \phi(N)$ and $m \notin N$ then s is not ϕ -prime to N , so $s \in P \cap S$, which a contradiction. Thus $m \in N$. If $sm \in \phi(N)$ then $m/1 = sm/s \in S^{-1}(\phi(N))$ which implies that $m \in S^{-1}(\phi(N)) \cap M$. Therefore $(S^{-1}N \cap M) = N \cup (S^{-1}(\phi(N)) \cap M)$, so $(S^{-1}N \cap M) = N$ or $(S^{-1}N \cap M) = ((S^{-1}(\phi(N)) \cap M))$. But $S^{-1}N \neq S^{-1}(\phi(N))$, so $S^{-1}N \cap M \neq S^{-1}(\phi(N)) \cap M$. Thus $S^{-1}N \cap M = N$. $\square$

5 ϕ -2-Absorbing Submodules

In this section, we introduce the concept of ϕ -2-absorbing submodules which is a generalization to concept of 2-absorbing submodules. Let R be a commutative ring with identity and M be a unitary R -module. Let $S(M)$ be the set of all submodules of M , and $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function.

Definition 5.1. A proper submodule N of M is called ϕ -2-absorbing submodule if $r, s \in R, m \in M$ with $rs m \in N - \phi(N)$ implies that $rs \in (N : M)$ or $rm \in N$ or $sm \in N$.

Example 5.2. *Let R be a commutative ring. Let M be an R -module. Let $S(M)$ be the set of all submodules of M . Define the following type of the functions $\phi_\alpha : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ and the corresponding ϕ_α -primal submodules as follows :*

- 1) $\phi_\emptyset : \phi_\emptyset(N) = \emptyset, \forall N \in S(M)$, defines 2-absorbing submodules.
- 2) $\phi_0 : \phi_0(N) = \{0\}, \forall N \in S(M)$, then defines weakly 2-absorbing submodules.
- 3) $\phi_1 : \phi_1(N) = N, \forall N \in S(M)$, defines any submodule N .

- 4) $\phi_2 : \phi_2(N) = (N : M)N, \forall N \in S(M)$, defines almost 2-absorbing submodules.
 5) $\phi_w : \phi_w(N) = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} (N : M)^i N, \forall N \in S(M)$, defines ϕ_w -2-absorbing submodule.
 6) $\phi_n : \phi_n(N) = (N : M)^{n-1}N, \forall n \geq 2, \forall N \in S(M)$, defines n -almost 2-absorbing submodules.

Remarks 5.3. (1) every 2-absorbing submodule is ϕ -2-absorbing submodule but the converse need not be true in general. For example, let $M = \mathbb{Z}_8$ be a $\mathbb{Z}$ module and let $N = \{0\}$. N is ϕ_0 (weakly)-2-absorbing submodule but not 2-absorbing submodule because $2 \cdot 2 \cdot 2 = 0 \in N$ and $4 \notin N$ and $4 \notin (N : M) = \{8n : n \in \mathbb{Z}\}$.

(2) Observe that $\phi_{\emptyset} \leq \phi_0 \leq \phi_w \leq \dots \leq \phi_{n+1} \leq \phi_n \leq \dots \leq \phi_2 \leq \phi_1$.

Proposition 5.4. Let R be a commutative ring and N be a submodule of R -module M .

(1) Let $\psi_1, \psi_2 : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be functions with $\psi_1 \leq \psi_2$. Then N is ψ_1 -2-absorbing submodule implies N is ψ_2 -2-absorbing.

(2) N is 2-absorbing $\implies N$ is weakly 2-absorbing $\implies N$ is ϕ_w -2-absorbing $\implies N$ is ϕ_{n+1} -2-absorbing $\implies \phi_n$ -2-absorbing ($n \geq 2$) $\implies N$ is ϕ_2 -2-absorbing.

Proof. (1) Assume that N is ϕ_1 -2-absorbing submodule of M . Let $rsm \in N - \phi_2(N)$ for $r, s \in R, m \in M$ then $rsm \in N - \phi_1(N)$. Since N is ϕ_1 -2-absorbing, $rs \in (N : M)$ or $rm \in N$ or $sm \in N$. Hence N is ϕ_2 -2-absorbing submodule of M .

(2) This follows from (1) and the ordering of the ϕ_{α} 's given in Example 5.2 and Remarks 5.3. □

Theorem 5.5. Let $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be function. Let N be a ϕ -2-absorbing submodule of M . If $(N : M)N \not\subseteq \phi(N)$, then N is a 2-absorbing submodule of M .

Proof. Let $r, s \in R$ and $m \in M$ be such that $rsm \in N$. If $rsm \notin \phi(N)$ and since N is ϕ -2-absorbing then we have $rs \in (N : M)$ or $rm \in N$ or $sm \in N$. So let $rsm \in \phi(N)$. In this case we may assume that $rsN \subseteq \phi(N)$. Because if $rsN \not\subseteq \phi(N)$, then there exists $p \in N$ such that $rsp \notin \phi(N)$, so that $rs(m + p) \in N - \phi(N)$. Therefore $rs \in (N : M)$ or $r(m + p) \in N$ or $s(m + p) \in N$ and hence $rs \in (N : M)$ or $rm \in N$ or $sm \in N$. Second we may assume that $(N : M)m \in \phi(N)$. If this is not the case, there exists $u \in (N : M)$ such that $um \notin \phi(N)$ and so $(r + u)sm \in N - \phi(N)$. Since N is a ϕ -2-absorbing submodule, we have $(r + u)s \in (N : M)$ or $(r + u)m \in N$ or $sm \in N$. Thus $rs \in (N : M)$ or $rm \in N$ or $sm \in N$. Now since $(N : M)N \not\subseteq \phi(N)$, there exist $v \in (N : M)$ and $p \in N$ such that $vp \notin \phi(N)$. So $(r + v)s(m + p) \in N - \phi(N)$, and hence $(r + v)s \in (N : M)$ or $(r + v)(m + p) \in N$ or $s(m + p) \in N$. Therefore $rs \in (N : M)$ or $rm \in N$ or $sm \in N$. Thus N is 2-absorbing submodule. □

Corollary 5.6. Let N be a weakly 2-absorbing submodule of M such that $(N : M)N \neq 0$. Then N is a 2-absorbing submodule of M .

Proof. In the above Theorem set $\phi = \phi_0$. □

Remark 5.7. Suppose that N is a ϕ -2-absorbing submodule of M such that $\phi(N) \subseteq (N : M)N$ and N is not 2-absorbing submodule then by Theorem 5.5, we have $\phi(N) = (N : M)N$. In particular if N is weakly 2-absorbing submodule but not 2-absorbing then $(N : M)N = 0$.

Theorem 5.8. [13] Let $R = R_1 \times R_2$ such that each R_i is a commutative ring with identity. Let M_i be R_i -module $\forall i \in \{1, 2\}$ and $M = M_1 \times M_2$ be an R -module with $(r_1, r_2)(m_1, m_2) = (r_1m_1, r_2m_2)$, where $r_i \in R_i, m_i \in M_i \forall i \in \{1, 2\}$. Then we have:

(1) If N_1 is a 2-absorbing submodule of M_1 , then $N_1 \times M_2$ is a 2-absorbing submodule of M .

(2) If N_2 is a 2-absorbing submodule of M_2 , then $M_1 \times N_2$ is a 2-absorbing submodule of M .

Proof. Because the proof of (1) and (2) are similar, So we only prove (1). Hence suppose that N_1 is a 2-absorbing submodule of M_1 and let $r_1, s_1 \in R_1, r_2, s_2 \in R_2, m_1 \in M_1$ and m_2

$\in M_2$ such that $(r_1, r_2)(s_1, s_2)(m_1, m_2) = (r_1 s_1 m_1, r_2 s_2 m_2) \in N_1 \times M_2$. then $r_1 s_1 m_1 \in N_1$. Since N_1 is 2-absorbing submodule of M_1 , So $r_1 s_1 \in (N_1 : M_1)$ or $r_1 m_1 \in N_1$ or $s_1 m_1 \in N_1$. So $(r_1, r_2)(s_1, s_2) = (r_1 s_1, r_2 s_2) \in (N_1 : M_1) \times (M_2 : M_2) = (N_1 \times M_2 : M_1 \times M_2)$ or $(r_1, r_2)(m_1, m_2) \in N_1 \times M_2$ or $(s_1, s_2)(m_1, m_2) \in N_1 \times M_2$. Hence $N_1 \times M_2$ is 2-absorbing submodule of M . $\square$

Example 5.9. The above theorem is not true for correspondence ϕ - 2-absorbing submodules in general, for example if N_1 is a ϕ_0 -2-absorbing submodule of M_1 then $N_1 \times M_2$ is not necessarily a ϕ_0 - 2-absorbing submodule of $M_1 \times M_2$. Let $R_1 = R_2 = M_1 = M_2 = \mathbb{Z}_8$ and suppose that $N_1 = \{0\}$ then evidently N_1 is a ϕ_0 -2-absorbing submodule of M_1 . However, $0 \neq (2,1)(2,1)(2,1) \in N_1 \times M_2$ and $(2, 1)(2,1) = (4,1) \notin (N_1 \times M_2 : M_1 \times M_2)$ and $(2,1)(2,1) \notin N_1 \times M_2$. Thus $N_1 \times M_2$ is not ϕ_0 -absorbing submodule of M .

Proposition 5.10. Let R_1 and R_2 be two commutative rings, M_1 and M_2 be R_1 and R_2 - modules respectively. Let $M = M_1 \times M_2$ and define $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function. Suppose that N_1 is a weakly 2-absorbing submodule of M_1 such that $\{0\} \times M_2 \subseteq \phi(N_1 \times M_2)$. Then $N_1 \times M_2$ is a ϕ -2-absorbing submodule of $M_1 \times M_2$.

Proof. Let $r_1, s_1 \in R_1, r_2, s_2 \in R_2, x_1 \in M_1$ and $x_2 \in M_2$. Let $(r_1, r_2)(s_1, s_2)(x_1, x_2) = (r_1 s_1 x_1, r_2 s_2 x_2) \in N_1 \times M_2 - \phi(N_1 \times M_2)$. Since $N_1 \times M_2 - \phi(N_1 \times M_2) \subseteq N_1 \times M_2 - \{0\} \times M_2 = (N_1 - \{0\}) \times M_2$, so we have $r_1 s_1 x_1 \in N_1 - \{0\}$ and by the assumption on N_1 we have $r_1 s_1 \in (N_1 :_{R_1} M_1)$ or $r_1 x_1 \in N_1$ or $s_1 x_1 \in N_1$. If $r_1 s_1 \in (N_1 :_{R_1} M_1)$ then $(r_1, r_2)(s_1, s_2) = (r_1 s_1, r_2 s_2) \in (N_1 :_{R_1} M_1) \times R_2 = (N_1 \times M_2 :_{R_1 \times R_2} M_1 \times M_2)$. If $r_1 x_2 \in N_1$ then $(r_1, r_2)(x_1, x_2) = (r_1 x_1, r_2 x_2) \in N_1 \times M_2$. If $s_1 x_1 \in N_1$ then $(s_1, s_2)(x_1, x_2) = (s_1 x_1, s_2 x_2) \in N_1 \times M_2$. Therefore $N_1 \times M_2$ is ϕ -2-absorbing submodule of M . $\square$

In the next theorem we give characterizations of ϕ -2-absorbing submodules.

Theorem 5.11. Let N be a proper submodule of M and let $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function. Then the following are equivalent:

- (i) N is a ϕ -2-absorbing submodule of M ;
- (ii) for any $r, s \in R$, with $rs \notin (N : M)$, we have $(N : rs) = (N : r) \cup (N : s) \cup (\phi(N) : rs)$;
- (iii) for any $r, s \in R$, with $rs \notin (N : M)$, we have, $(N : rs) = (N : r)$ or $(N : rs) = (\phi(N) : s)$ or $(N : rs) = (\phi(N) : rs)$.

Proof. (i) $\implies$ (ii) Let $m \in (N : rs)$ then $rsm \in N$. If $rsm \notin \phi(N)$ then N is a ϕ -2-absorbing submodule of M implies $rm \in N$ or $sm \in N$, that is $m \in (N : r)$ or $m \in (N : s)$. If $rsm \in \phi(N)$ then $m \in (\phi(N) : rs)$. As we may assume that $\phi(N) \subseteq N$, the other inclusion always hold.

(ii) $\implies$ (iii) If an ideal is the union of two ideals, it is equal to one of them.

(iii) $\implies$ (i) Let $rsm \in N - \phi(N)$ with $rs \notin (N : M)$ then $m \in (N : rs)$ and $m \notin (\phi(N) : rs)$, so $m \in (N : r)$ or $m \in (N : s)$ that is, $rm \in N$ or $sm \in N$. $\square$

Theorem 5.12. Let M be an R -module and let $\phi : S(M) \rightarrow S(M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$ be a function. Let N be a ϕ -2-absorbing submodule of M .

- (i) If $L \subseteq N$ is a submodule of M , then N/L is a ϕ_L -2-absorbing submodule of M/L .
- (ii) Suppose that S is a multiplicatively closed subset of R such that $S^{-1}N \neq S^{-1}M$ and $S^{-1}(\phi(N)) \subseteq (S^{-1}\phi)(S^{-1}N)$ with $(N :_R M) \cap S = \emptyset$. Let $S^{-1}\phi : S(S^{-1}M) \rightarrow S(S^{-1}M) \cup \{\emptyset\}$. Then $S^{-1}N$ is an $(S^{-1}\phi)$ -2-absorbing submodule of $S^{-1}M$.

Proof. (i) Let $r, s \in R$ and $\bar{x} \in M/L$ with $rs\bar{x} \in N/L - \phi_L(N/L)$, where $\bar{x} = x + L$, for some $x \in M$. By the definition of ϕ_L , this gives that $rsx \in N - (\phi(N) + L)$. So we have $rsx \in N - \phi(N)$, which gives that $rs \in (N : M)$ or $rx \in N$ or $sx \in N$. Therefore $rs \in (N/L : M/L)$ or $r\bar{x} \in N/L$ or $s\bar{x} \in N/L$ and so N/L is ϕ_L - 2-absorbing submodule.

(ii) Let $a/s, b/w \in S^{-1}R$ and $x/t \in S^{-1}M$ with $abx/swt \in S^{-1}N - (S^{-1}\phi)(S^{-1}N)$. Then by our assumption $abx/swt \in S^{-1}N - S^{-1}(\phi(N))$. Therefore there exists $u \in S$ such that

$uabx \in N - \phi(N)$, (note that for each $v \in S$, $vabx \notin \phi(N)$). Since N is ϕ -2-absorbing submodule and $(N : M) \cap S = \emptyset$, we have $uab \in (N : M)$ or $ax \in N$ or $bx \in N$. Therefore $ab/sw \in S^{-1}(N :_R M) \subseteq (S^{-1}N :_{S^{-1}R} S^{-1}M)$ or $ax/st \in S^{-1}N$ or $bx/wt \in S^{-1}N$. Hence $S^{-1}N$ is an $(S^{-1}\phi)$ -2-absorbing submodule of $S^{-1}M$. $\square$

Proposition 5.13. *Let $R = R_1 \times R_2 \times \dots \times R_n$ and $M = M_1 \times M_2 \times \dots \times M_n$ be an R -module, where R_i is a commutative ring and M_i is an R_i -module, for each $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Let $N = N_1 \times N_2 \times \dots \times N_n$ be a ϕ -2-absorbing submodule of M , where N_i is a submodule of M_i and let $\psi_i : S(M_i) \rightarrow S(M_i) \cup \{\emptyset\} \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and $\phi(N) = \psi_1(N_1) \times \psi_2(N_2) \times \dots \times \psi_n(N_n)$. Then N_j is a ψ_j -2-absorbing submodule of M_j , for each j with $N_j \neq M_j$.*

Proof. Let $x_j \in M_j$ and $a_j, b_j \in R_j$ such that $a_j b_j x_j \in N_j - \psi_j(N_j)$. Thus $(1, 1, \dots, 1, a_j, \dots, 1) \cdot (1, 1, \dots, 1, b_j, \dots, 1) \cdot (0, 0, \dots, 0, x_j, \dots, 0) = (0, 0, \dots, 0, a_j b_j x_j, \dots, 0) \in N - \phi(N)$, but N is ϕ -2-absorbing submodule. Therefore, $(1, 1, \dots, 1, a_j, \dots, 1) \cdot (1, 1, \dots, 1, b_j, \dots, 1) \in (N : M)$ or $(1, 1, \dots, 1, a_j, \dots, 1) \cdot (0, 0, \dots, 0, x_j, 0, \dots, 0) \in N$ or $(1, 1, \dots, 1, b_j, \dots, 1) \cdot (0, 0, \dots, 0, x_j, 0, \dots, 0) \in N$. So we have $a_j b_j \in (N_j : M_j)$ or $a_j x_j \in N_j$ or $b_j x_j \in N_j$. Thus N_j is ψ_j -2-absorbing submodule for each j . $\square$

Corollary 5.14. *Let $R = R_1 \times R_2 \times \dots \times R_n$ and $M = M_1 \times M_2 \times \dots \times M_n$ an R -module and $N = N_1 \times N_2 \times \dots \times N_n$, where R_i is a commutative ring and M_i is an R_i -module and N_i is a submodule of M_i , for $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Let N be a ϕ_n -2-absorbing submodule of M . Then N_j is a ϕ_n -2-absorbing submodule of M_j , for each j with $N_j \neq M_j$ and $n \geq 2$.*

Proof. We have $\phi_n(N) = (N:M)^{n-1}N = (N_1:M)^{n-1}N_1 \times (N_2:M)^{n-1}N_2 \times \dots \times (N_n:M)^{n-1}N_n = \phi_n(N_1) \times \phi_n(N_2) \times \dots \times \phi_n(N_n)$. So the result follows by Proposition 5.13. $\square$

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